

Chuci zhangju

By Heng Du, University of Arizona

Entry tags: Cosmology, Early Chinese Traditions, Religious Group, Early Chinese text, Text, Cosmogony, Yellow and Yangzi Rivers Region

The /Chuci zhangju/ 楚辭章句 (The Section and Sentence Commentary to the /Verses of the Chu/) is a collection of verses written in the Chuci—or “Verses of the Chu”—genre, compiled and annotated by Wang Yi 王逸 (fl. 130–140 CE), a scholar-official of the Eastern Han (25–220). The word “Chu” designates the watery southern region of present-day China along the Yangzi River, at one point an independent kingdom before its conquest in 223 BCE by the expanding Qin empire (221–206 BCE). The founders of the subsequent Han empires (202 BCE–220 CE) hailed from the Chu region. As one of the two oldest extant collections of Chinese verses, the /Chuci/ is traditionally conceived of as the younger, southern, and “romantic” counterpart to the /The Classic of Poetry/ (Shijing 詩經), the older, northern, and canonical anthology associated with the culture of the Zhou polity (ca.1046–256 BCE). The term “Chuci” can be used to designate both this anthology and the Chuci genre or style (also known as the /sao/ 騷). Poems written in the Chuci or /sao/ style employ a distinctive meter and a specialized repertoire of vocabularies and formulae, in addition to references to the landscape and mythology of the south. They also tend to be fantastical and elegiac in content and tone. || Wang Yi ascribes the first seven titles (in the received 12th-century /Chuci buzhu/ 楚辭補注 edition), roughly the earliest layer of this compilation, to the archetypical poet of the Chuci genre, Qu Yuan 屈原 (trad. 343–290 BCE). An upright minister of Chu, Qu Yuan is said to have been exiled on account of slander and wrote a body of verses during his banishment, before drowning himself in the Miluo 汨羅 river. The most well-known among these verses is the first piece of the compilation, “Li sao” 離騷 (Encountering Sorrow). Except for the final piece associated with Wang Yi, the remaining titles are attributed either to Qu Yuan’s purported disciples or to literary figures of the Western Han (202 BCE–7 CE). The earliest historical event known to be associated with this text took place in 139 BCE, when Liu An 劉安 (179?–112 BCE), the King of Huainan, paid a visit to his nephew, Emperor Wu of Han (r.141–87 BCE), and is said to have presented Chuci materials to the young emperor (/Hanshu/ 44.2145). Wang Yi claims as the basis of his commentary in /Chuci zhangju/ earlier exegetical writings, which include a work attributed to Liu An. || Prior to its introduction to the Han imperial court, verses composed in the Chuci genre might have been employed in ritual and performative settings, although the extant poems in /Chuci zhangju/ are best understood as literary rewritings that indirectly preserve traces of the earlier ritual contexts. Each piece within the poetic suite “Nine Songs” (Jiu ge 九歌), for instance, addresses a god or a type of spirit in a pantheon of deities, most of whom are associated with nature. Two of the three “Summons” (/zhao/ 招) pieces, such as “Summoning the Soul” (Zhao hun 招魂), call upon deceased spirits, and might have evolved from funerary chants. “Heavenly Questions” (Tianwen 天問) contains over 150 questions concerning cosmogony, cosmology, legendary and historical heroes, including the kings of the Chu state. “Far Roaming” (Yuan you 遠遊) suggests a process of self-cultivation or even self-divinization. Some of the motifs and formulae appear to have religious significance, such as the failed quests for goddesses and heavenly processions encircling a mandala-like cosmos. || The formation process of the anthology /Chuci zhangju/ attests to the incorporation of this body of materials into Han elite literary culture. The composition of the written pieces in this anthology involves the reworking and re-interpretation of existing verses as the literary compositions of the scholar-official class, whose ethos is embodied by the archpoet Qu Yuan. Its later, imitative pieces, along with its exegetical writings, are centered around the political and moral concerns of the scholar-officials. Formulaic phrases that might have once been associated with ritual purification, for example, became metaphors for moral purity in the context of court politics. Since the Han, composing Chuci verses and imitating the /Chuci zhangju/ often functioned as a space of negotiation between political loyalty and dissent. || The /Chuci zhangju/ also has its legacy in popular culture. Folk worship of Qu Yuan during the Duanwu 端午 (Fifth Day of the Fifth Lunar Month) became one of the major

yearly festivities in traditional and contemporary China. The commemoration of the drowned poet serves as the etiological explanation for customs such as the dragon boat race. || In existing scholarship, the Chuci corpus has often been understood through the lens of shamanism—translators from Arthur Waley to Gopal Sukhu have rendered the religious specialist “wu” 巫 as “shaman”—which is nevertheless a much-debated interpretative framework. Due to the near absence of direct evidence external to the text, reconstructions of the time, place, belief systems, and practices of its earlier religious contexts are at best educated guesses. This entry focuses on the formation process of the /Chuci zhangju/ as a literary anthology in the Han imperial and elite circle, between Liu An’s visit in 139 BCE and Wang Yi’s period of activities. It will nevertheless acknowledge the religious elements explicitly mentioned within the poems, such as its pantheon and cosmology.

Date Range: 139 BCE - 140 CE

Region: Han empires

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, China

After the short-lived Qin dynasty (221–206 BCE), the Han empires (202 BCE–220 CE) were the second set of polities that ruled over the heartland of present-day China through a unified imperial system. The Liu clan who founded the Western Han (202 BCE–7 CE) emerged from the Chu region along the Yangzi River. Around the beginning of the 1st century CE, an affinal member of the imperial family seized power and founded the Xin Dynasty (9–23 CE). After a period of civil strife, a distant member of the Liu clan eventually founded the Eastern Han (25–220) that reunified the empire. The seat of the imperial house was moved from the western capital of Chang'an (modern-day Xi'an) to the eastern capital Luoyang.

Status of Readership:

✓ Elite

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: /Chuci buzhu/ 楚辭補注. Compiled by Wang Yi 王逸 (fl. 130–140), Commentary by Hong Xingzu 洪興祖 (1090–1155). Beijing: Zhonghua shuju, 1983.
- Source 2: /Chuci jijiao jishi/ 楚辭集校集釋. Commentary by Cui Fuzhang 崔富章 and Li Daming 李大明. Wuhan: Hubei jiaoyu chubanshe, 2002.
- Source 3: Hawkes, David, trans. /The Songs of the South: An Ancient Chinese Anthology of Poems by Qu Yuan and Other Poets/. Harmondsworth: Penguin, 1985.

Notes: The received redaction, the Chuci buzhu 楚辭補注 (Supplements and Annotations to the Verses of the Chu), preserves the prefatory and commentarial writings of Chuci zhangju, with the addition of an extensive subcommentary by its own author, Hong Xingzu 洪興祖 (1090–1155). Hong’s notes allow for the reconstruction of a no longer attested redaction, the Chuci shiwen 楚辭釋文 (Explications of the Texts of the Verses of the Chu), compiled before the Southern Tang (937–976). The Chuci shiwen follows a different chapter sequence, which, as Tang Bingzheng 湯炳正 demonstrates, is most certainly closer to

Wang Yi's Chuci zhangju. || /Chuci jijiao jishi/ 楚辭集校集釋 in four volumes compile together over two millennia of commentarial writings, including the works of modern and contemporary scholars in East Asia. || /The Songs of the South/ is the most widely used English translation. As the translator David Hawkes is also a scholar of Chuci, his translation is accompanied by helpful overviews and extensive scholarly discussions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.schimmelpfennig-research.eu/ccbib/>

– Source 1 Description: A bibliography of Chuci research selected by Michael Schimmelpfennig (last updated 2010).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

– Source 1 URL: <https://ctext.org/chu-ci>

– Source 1 Description: Full text of the received Chuci, along with the majority of received early Chinese texts. This website allows users to view machine-identified textual parallels of a given passage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

General Variables

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Methods of Composition

– Printed with moveable type

Notes: Most premodern printed edition of Chuci materials, just as most other premodern Chinese print production, make use of woodblock printing rather than moveable type.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Number of sheets

– Bound

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

– Written

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Inked

–with Ink

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

– Paper

Notes: The transmission of /Chuci zhangju/ during China's medieval period (3rd c.-10th c.) would have largely relied on paper manuscripts. For fragments of medieval manuscripts preserved in Japan and the earliest printed edition with extant reprints (13th century), see Hawkes, "Ch'u tz'u."

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Specify type of paper

–Specify: The production of this text was not restricted to any specific type of paper.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

– Bamboo

Notes: The majority of early Chinese texts during this time period (mid-2nd century BCE to mid-2nd century CE) were likely written on bamboo and wood slips and tablets. Given the elite interest in the Chuci materials, silk copies of the Chuci zhangju or related materials would not be a surprise, although it is not yet directly attested. Fragments of Han period bamboo manuscripts bearing partial textual parallels to the received Chuci corpus have been found (see bibliography).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

– Other [specify]: The production of this text did not entail material modification.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Materiality

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Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Production & Intended Audience

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Notes: Polities, such as the Kingdom of Huainan and the Han imperial court, played a role in the formation process of /Chuci zhangju/. The Prince of Huainan (179?-122 BCE), known as a patron for scholarly and literary activities, is said to have presented Chuci materials to Emperor Wu of Han (r.141-87 BCE), which might have constituted the earliest layer of the received compilation. The Chuci materials

could have been redacted as part of the systemization and reorganization of the imperial library during the last decades of the 1st century BCE. At the same time, none of these polities were specifically interested in patronizing the production of Chuci materials, nor did the formation process of /Chuci zhangju/ rely on state sponsorship.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Notes: The pieces preserved in /Chuci zhangju/ are written in Classical Chinese but employing a distinctive repertoire of poetic diction that likely had roots in ritual practices and perhaps even religious worldviews. But Han elites by and large seem to view this body of materials as literary compositions. The specialized vocabularies are extensively glossed in the /Chuci zhangju/—though not unlike most other classical texts—which could be indicating that new readers were in need of reading aid. At the same time, the /History of the Han/ records recitation of Chuci verses for the emperor by a bard from the Chu region (/Hanshu/ 64b), which could suggest that such texts were at least to some extent aurally comprehensible to imperial elites.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– Yes

Notes: The exact nature and context of the relevant ritual practices are unknown. The three "Summons" chapters, however, are generally understood to be associated with chants performed during the funerary process, addressing the spirit of the deceased.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is it orally recited?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is there any particular affect of the oral recitation of the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is it read?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is there any particular affect on the reader of the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is there any particular affect on the audience of the recitation?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Describe the nature of the ritual practice?

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the text employed in large scale rituals?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the text employed in small scale rituals?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ On average, how many participants are present?

– I don't know

Notes: The exact nature and context of the relevant ritual practices are unknown. The three "Summons" chapters, however, are generally understood to be associated with chants performed during the funerary process, addressing the spirit of the deceased.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ How often do the rituals take place?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there synchronic practices?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there other substances (such as food or drink, for example) that are consumed during rituals?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

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Region: Han

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" and "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) chapters suggest that the "hun" 魂 (soul) of the deceased can exist beyond death or wander away from the body. Other terms associated with the mind-spirit, such as "shen" 神 (spirit, god) and "ling" 靈 (numinous, spirit), occur throughout the compilation. "Hymn to the Fallen" ends with "Their bodies may have died, but their souls are living: Heroes among the shades their valiant souls will be" 身既死兮神以靈，子魂魄兮為鬼雄 (translated by Hawkes).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: During this time period, spirit and souls were generally conceptualized as purer forms of the material that make up the body, namely different types of "qi" 氣 (vapor, pneuma). "Far Roaming" (Yuan you 遠遊) associates the cultivation of one's mind-spirit with the refinement of breadth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: This is largely absent from the /Chuci zhangju/ except for in the "Heavenly Question" (Tianwen 天問) chapter, where the high god(s) (di 帝) do appear to punish or support several heroes and rulers, but their motivations are not entirely clear. Since the Han period interpreters have found this chapter to be particularly difficult. Wang Yi's commentary often reads such /di/ figures as earthly rulers comparable to the emperors of China's imperial period, who also referred to themselves as /di/.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" chapters suggest that the hun 魂 (soul) of can wander away from the body after death. "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) ends with "Their bodies may have died, but their souls are living: Heroes among the shades their valiant souls will be" 身既死兮神以靈，子魂魄兮為鬼雄 (translated by Hawkes).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: One of the central moral dilemmas revolves around how to navigate a corrupt age: whether to conform to its norms in the interest of self-preservation or to uphold what it considers to be universal morality. The "Divination" (Buju 卜居) and "The Fisherman" (Yufu 漁父) chapters, for example, clearly articulate this binary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only one class of society

Notes: This is not entirely clear. In one interpretation, this text expresses largely the moral stance of the male elite shi 士 class.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Even though during the imperial period, readers largely interpret the protagonists of Chuci as male literati elites, the text does not dictate that its values are restricted to only one specific social group. At least one woman writer, Wu Zao 吴藻 (1799-1862), has written a literary work (a play entitled "Qiao ying 乔影") imitating Qu Yuan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

— No

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there multiple versions of the text?

— Yes

Notes: Early sources suggest there were alternative understandings of which poems were authored by Qu Yuan during the Han period. Wang Yi's commentary also suggests there were at least several commented redactions of Chuci materials before his. Subsequently, there are significant changes to the sequence of the chapters between Wang Yi's /Chuci zhangju/ and the received edition, in addition to other small textual variations reflected in the commentarial tradition and extant witnesses. But such variations are to be expected in the transmission history of early texts.

Reference: Chan, Timothy. "The Jing/zhuan Structure of the Chuci Anthology: A New Approach to the Authorship of Some of the Poems". *T'oung Pao* 84 (1998): 293-327.

Reference: Du, Heng. "The Author's Two Bodies: The Death of Qu Yuan and the Birth of Chuci Zhangju 楚辭章句". *T'oung Pao* 105, no. 3-4 (2019): 259-314.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any means?

— Yes

Notes: However, we do not have direct access to these earlier and alternative versions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there debate about which version is proper?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: This is largely absent from the /Chuci zhangju/ except for in the "Heavenly Question" (Tianwen 天問) chapter, where the high god(s) (di 帝) do appear to punish or support several heroes and rulers, but their motivations are not entirely clear. Since the Han period interpreters have found this chapter to be particularly difficult. Wang Yi's commentary often reads such /di/ figures as earthly rulers comparable to the emperors of China's imperial period, who also referred to themselves as /di/.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) praises the fallen soldiers for their courage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

— Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

— Yes

Notes: Another recurring motif is the protagonists' spotless purity (expressed through terms such as "qing" 清, "jie" 潔, and "bai" 白) despite the constant threat of impurity and corruption. A related motif is the protagonists donning and consuming fragrant plants and flora, which are sources of purity but are not free from the danger of decay.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

— Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Cooperation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the protagonists are independent from their social contexts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Power/status/nobility

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: The term "beauty" (mei 美) is frequently employed in the early chapters as a positive term, in both physical and metaphorical senses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: Another recurring motif is the protagonists' spotless purity (expressed through terms such as "qing" 清, "jie" 潔, and "bai" 白) despite the constant threat of impurity and corruption. A related motif is the protagonists donning and consuming fragrant plants and flora, which are sources of purity but are not free from the danger of decay.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other important virtues

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Verses composed in the Chuci genre might have been employed in ritual and performative settings, although the extant poems in /Chuci zhangju/ are best understood as literary rewritings that indirectly preserve traces of the earlier ritual contexts. Having been absorbed into the Han elite literary culture, Chuci became an important literary genre in the Chinese tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Other

– Other [specify]: The Chuci corpus was imitated throughout the Chinese literary tradition, often as a space for expressing political concerns and dissent. The resulting body of verses are often referred to as the "sao" 騷 genre or style.

Reference: Schneider, Laurence A.. A Madman of Chu. University of California Press, 2021.

https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Madman_of_Ch.html?hl=&id=QfnnDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Su, Fu. "When the South Matters: Imagination of Chu and Classicization of Chuci (verses of Chu)". PhD diss., Princeton University, 2019.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" chapters are generally understood to be associated with chants performed during the funerary process, addressing the spirit of the deceased. According to Miranda Brown's reconstruction, this "soul calling" ritual takes place during the first three days after death, a waiting period partly functioning as a guarantee that the deceased is indeed dead. At the end of these three days, the deceased would be dressed in the burial garment and placed in a coffin. Two of the three "Summons" chapters address the soul of the deceased. To entice the soul's return, they describe in detail the treacherous landscapes of all directions, as well as the enjoyments of the humanly realm.

Reference: Brown, Miranda. *Politics of Mourning in Early China*, the. SUNY Press, 2012.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=kOXXa83xC2kC>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: The "summoning of soul," as a ritual practice, seems to have taken place during the first three days after death, before the preparation for burial.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: Cf. The "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) praises the fallen soldiers for their courage. Most of the other pieces in "Nine Songs" are addressed to nature deities and spirits. As far as I know, we do not know much about the ritual practices behind these pieces.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

— Yes

Notes: Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

— Yes

Notes: Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

— Yes

Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ A supreme high-god is present

— Yes

Notes: The term /di/ 帝 (high god; thearch; emperor) is referenced from time to time in the Chuci corpus. This term refers to the highest god in oracle bone inscription (the earliest extant corpus of religious texts in the Chinese tradition) and appears to be a sky god. Rulers, pre-imperial and imperial, retraced their genealogies to various /di/. The first emperor of Qin changed the appellation of the highest ruler from "King" (wang 王) to "August Thearch/August Emperor" (huangdi 皇帝), thus blurring or complicating the religious significance of this term and further accelerating the tendency to euhemeristically interpret /di/ in earlier texts as historical rulers. Within the /Chuci zhangju/, the protagonist of "Encountering Sorrow" (Li sao 離騷) famously claims to be the descendent of a /di/ named Gaoyang 高陽 (i.e., 顓頊), who was understood to be the forefather of the Chu kings. The opening framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂) features a dialogue between a /di/ and a religious specialist (wu 巫). Whether such /di/ were understood as gods, divine rulers, or a historical rulers likely depended on the context of performance or reading. Writings by scholar-officials from the early imperial period often negatively portray emperors' self-divinizing practices, suggesting the coexistence of competing religious views.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

— Yes

Notes: During the period under consideration, the term for the high god, di 帝, has been incorporated into the title of the emperor, "huangdi" 皇帝 (the August thearch)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god
— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites
— Yes

Notes: Some of the rulers from pre-imperial and imperial periods retraced their genealogies to various /di/ (high gods; emperors).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites
— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good
— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other features of the supreme high god
— Specify: The text does not specify much.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world
— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs
— I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region
– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is unrestrict outside of sample region
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be hurt?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be tricked?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: We do not learn much about the features of the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: The opening framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂) portrays a dialogue between the high god (di 帝) and the world below through a religious specialist (wu 巫). In "Heavenly Questions" (Tianwen 天問), a /di/ can receive sacrifice, send down a hero to instigate dynastic overthrow, favor and punish rulers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

Notes: The text of the framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" is potentially fragmentary or corrupted. The /wu/ specialist in his reply to the high god mentions the phrase "Master of Dreams" (zhang meng 掌夢) but it is unclear what it refers to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other form of communication with living

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Notes: The barrier between humans and gods (and the breaching of this barrier) is

thematized throughout this corpus, through motifs such as the quest for the goddesses or the attempt to ascend heaven's gate. It is unclear whether the text presents itself as a medium for overcoming such a barrier.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Aside from the presence of deceased spirits in the "Summons" (zhao 招) chapters and "Hymn to the Fallen" (guo shang 國殤), the protagonist in "Encountering Sorrow" (Li sao 離騷) seems to be traveling back in time during his heavenly ascensions and potentially interacting with figures from the past. This time travel, however, could also be understood figuratively.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Human spirits can be seen

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Human spirits can be physically felt

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The moral justification for the archpoet Qu Yuan's purported suicide was a source of debate during the Han period. The voices of protagonists occasionally articulate the preference for death over compromising their moral integrity. At the same time, self-sacrifice is not required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Chuci poems mention a host of nature gods (such as the god and goddess of the Xiang River 湘) as well as supernatural creatures (such as dragons).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

— Yes

Notes: Some of the pieces in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite seem to be written from the perspectives of the divine beings (or possibly those of ritual performers who impersonate the gods). They contain expressions of positive emotions such as the experience of delight upon hearing music.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

— I don't know

Notes: "Heavenly Questions" (Tianwen 天問) recounts the High God sending down punishment. Some of the pieces in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite seem to be written from the perspectives of the divine beings (or possibly those of ritual performers who impersonate the gods and spirits). They contain expressions of negative emotions such as sad longing, though in most of these pieces it is difficult to fully determine whether it expresses the perspective of the divine beings or of the ritual specialists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

— Specify: We do not learn much about the features of these supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Each piece in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite is addressed to a god or types of spirits, collectively evoking the possibility of something akin to a pantheon of supernatural beings associated with nature. The sequence of the poems roughly suggests a hierarchy, for it begins with sky gods such as "The Great Unity, The August Lord of the East" (Donghuang taiyi 東皇太一) and "The Lord within the Clouds" (Yunzhong jun 雲中君) and ends with songs to a mountain ghost and to fallen warriors. Other poems in the suites are addressed to the god and goddess of the Xiang River 湘, Masters of Fate, the sun god, and the Earl of the Yellow River.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the gods appear to be associated with specific rivers, such as the Xiang River or the Yellow River.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Other organization of pantheon?

–Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Traditional scholarship, by and large, interprets the speaker of the first poem of this corpus, "Li sao," as the minister Qu Yuan. More recent scholarship points out that the language of the opening lines suggests the descent of a divine being. The desire to transgress the separation between the human and the divine is thematized by the Chuci genre, through topos such as failed trysts with a goddess or attempts to transcend the heavenly gate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the high god (di 帝), various deities (majority of whom are associated with nature), human spirits (hun 魂 and po 魄), and monsters dwelling in exotic outskirts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the framing narrative of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂), the high god (di 帝) communicates with the "wu" 巫 (spirit-medium).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: Monstrous

Notes: The three "Summons" (zhao 招) chapters enumerate exotic creatures at the outer extremes of the world in order to inspire fear in the wandering spirits and hasten their homecoming. Examples of such monsters include soul-catching giants, cannibals, venomous cobra, and nine-headed serpent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– Yes

Notes: Early sources suggest there were alternative understandings of which poems were authored by Qu Yuan during the Han period. Wang Yi's commentary also suggests there were at least several commented redactions of Chuci materials before his. Subsequently, there are significant changes to the sequence of the chapters between Wang Yi's /Chuci zhangju/ and the received edition, in addition to other small textual variations reflected in the commentarial tradition and extant witnesses. But such variations are to be expected in the transmission history of early texts.

Reference: Chan, Timothy. "The Jing/zhuàn Structure of the Chuci Anthology: A New Approach to the Authorship of Some of the Poems". *T'oung Pao* 84 (1998): 293–327.

Reference: Du, Heng. "The Author's Two Bodies: The Death of Qu Yuan and the Birth of Chuci Zhangju 楚辭章句". *T'oung Pao* 105, no. 3-4 (2019): 259–314.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are multiple versions viewed as proper?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ If multiple versions are proper, is there a differentiation among versions by any

means?

– Yes

Notes: However, we do not have direct access to these earlier and alternative versions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is there debate about which version is proper?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

Notes: Verses composed in the Chuci genre might have been employed in ritual and performative settings, although the extant poems in /Chuci zhangju/ are best understood as literary rewritings that indirectly preserve traces of the earlier ritual contexts. Having been absorbed into the Han elite literary culture, Chuci became an important literary genre in the Chinese tradition.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: The Chuci corpus was imitated throughout the Chinese literary tradition, often

as a space for expressing political concerns and dissent. The resulting body of verses are often referred to as the "sao" 騷 genre or style.

Reference: Schneider, Laurence A. *A Madman of Chu*. University of California Press, 2021.
https://books.google.com/books/about/A_Madman_of_Ch.html?hl=&id=QfnnDwAAQBAJ.

Reference: Su, Fu. "When the South Matters: Imagination of Chu and Classicization of Chuci (verses of Chu)". PhD diss., Princeton University, 2019.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary? (Select all that apply)

– Other [specify]: None of the above

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" and "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) chapters suggest that the "hun" 魂 (soul) of the deceased can exist beyond death or wander away from the body. Other terms associated

with the mind-spirit, such as "shen" 神 (spirit, god) and "ling" 靈 (numinous, spirit), occur throughout the compilation. "Hymn to the Fallen" ends with "Their bodies may have died, but their souls are living: Heroes among the shades their valiant souls will be" 身既死兮神以靈，子魂魄兮為鬼雄 (translated by Hawkes).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Spirit-Mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other parts?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body?

– No

Notes: During this time period, spirit and souls were generally conceptualized as purer forms of the material that make up the body, namely different types of "qi" 氣 (vapor, pneuma). "Far Roaming" (Yuan you 遠遊) associates the cultivation of one's mind-spirit with the refinement of breadth.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other spirit-body relationship?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Within conceptions of the mind: are there distinct notions of psychological states or aggregates?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do practitioners engage in debates about mind-body dualism?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are debates framed in other ways?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do practitioners distinguish between a corporeal body and an incorporeal soul or spirit?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Are there other sides or features of the debate?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ What are historical mainstream and minority positions?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" chapters suggest that the hun 魂 (soul) of can wander away from the body after death. "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) ends with "Their bodies may have died, but their souls are living: Heroes among the shades their valiant souls will be" 身既死兮神以靈，子魂魄兮為鬼雄 (translated by Hawkes).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses dicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– Yes

Notes: The "Summons" chapters are generally understood to be associated with chants performed

during the funerary process, addressing the spirit of the deceased. According to Miranda Brown's reconstruction, this "soul calling" ritual takes place during the first three days after death, a waiting period partly functioning as a guarantee that the deceased is indeed dead. At the end of these three days, the deceased would be dressed in the burial garment and placed in a coffin. Two of the three "Summons" chapters address the soul of the deceased. To entice the soul's return, they describe in detail the treacherous landscapes of all directions, as well as the enjoyments of the humanly realm.

Reference: Brown, Miranda. *Politics of Mourning in Early China*, the. SUNY Press, 2012.
<https://play.google.com/store/books/details?id=kOXXa83xC2kC>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do these practices take place at tombs/burial sites?

– No

Notes: The "summoning of soul," as a ritual practice, seems to have taken place during the first three days after death, before the preparation for burial.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Do these practices take place for the veneration OR worship of the dead?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: Cf. The "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) praises the fallen soldiers for their courage. Most of the other pieces in "Nine Songs" are addressed to nature deities and spirits. As far as I know, we do not know much about the ritual practices behind these pieces.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the worship of a deified human?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Notes: Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deceased person(s)?

– Yes

Notes: Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deified human?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ For the veneration of a deceased hero?

– Yes

Notes: Cf. the "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece in the suite "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ A supreme high-god is present

– Yes

Notes: The term /di/ 帝 (high god; thearch; emperor) is referenced from time to time in the Chuci corpus. This term refers to the highest god in oracle bone inscription (the earliest extant corpus of religious texts in the Chinese tradition) and appears to be a sky god. Rulers, pre-imperial and imperial, retraced their genealogies to various /di/. The first emperor of Qin changed the appellation of the highest ruler from "King" (wang 王) to "August Thearch/August Emperor" (huangdi 皇帝), thus blurring or complicating the religious significance of this term and further accelerating the tendency to euhemeristically interpret /di/ in earlier texts as historical rulers. Within the /Chuci zhangju/, the protagonist of "Encountering Sorrow" (Li sao 離騷) famously claims to be the descendent of a /di/ named Gaoyang 高陽 (i.e., 顓頊), who was

understood to be the forefather of the Chu kings. The opening framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂) features a dialogue between a /di/ and a religious specialist (wu 巫). Whether such /di/ were understood as gods, divine rulers, or a historical rulers likely depended on the context of performance or reading. Writings by scholar-officials from the early imperial period often negatively portray emperors' self-divinizing practices, suggesting the coexistence of competing religious views.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic or described in anthropomorphic terms

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The supreme high god is a sky deity

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god)

– Yes

Notes: During the period under consideration, the term for the high god, di 帝, has been incorporated into the title of the emperor, "huangdi" 皇帝 (the August thearch)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites

– Yes

Notes: Some of the rulers from pre-imperial and imperial periods retraced their genealogies to various /di/ (high gods; emperors).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other features of the supreme high god

– Specify: The text does not specify much.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is restricted to a particular domain of human affairs

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see you everywhere normally visible (in public)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knows basic character (personal essence)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight)

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Has other knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Has deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Exhibits positive emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Exhibits negative emotion

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Possesses Hunger?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be hurt?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be tricked?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Can be imprisoned?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural being other than the high god?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature

– Specify: We do not learn much about the features of the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living

– Yes

Notes: The opening framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂) portrays a dialogue between the high god (di 帝) and the world below through a religious specialist (wu 巫). In "Heavenly Questions" (Tianwen 天問), a /di/ can receive sacrifice, send down a hero to instigate dynastic overthrow, favor and punish rulers.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In waking, everyday life

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In dreams

– I don't know

Notes: The text of the framing dialogue of "Summoning the Soul" is potentially fragmentary or corrupted. The /wu/ specialist in his reply to the high god mentions the phrase "Master of Dreams" (zhang meng 掌夢) but it is unclear what it refers to.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ In trance possession

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Through divination practices

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Only through religious specialists

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other form of communication with living

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Does the text make communication with supreme high-god possible?

– I don't know

Notes: The barrier between humans and gods (and the breaching of this barrier) is thematized throughout this corpus, through motifs such as the quest for the goddesses or the attempt to ascend heaven's gate. It is unclear whether the text presents itself as a medium for overcoming such a barrier.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Previously human spirits are present

– Yes

Notes: Aside from the presence of deceased spirits in the "Summons" (zhao 招) chapters and "Hymn to the Fallen" (guo shang 國殤), the protagonist in "Encountering Sorrow" (Li sao 離騷) seems to be traveling back in time during his heavenly ascensions and potentially interacting with figures from the past. This time travel, however, could also be understood figuratively.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits can be seen

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits have memory of life

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– Yes

Notes: Chuci poems mention a host of nature gods (such as the god and goddess of the Xiang River 湘) as well as supernatural creatures (such as dragons).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Supernatural beings can be seen

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Supernatural beings can be physically felt

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Non-human supernatural beings communicate with the living according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion

– Yes

Notes: Some of the pieces in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite seem to be written from the perspectives of the divine beings (or possibly those of ritual performers who impersonate the gods). They contain expressions of positive emotions such as the experience of delight upon hearing music.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion

– I don't know

Notes: "Heavenly Questions" (Tianwen 天問) recounts the High God sending down punishment. Some of the pieces in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite seem to be written from the perspectives of the divine beings (or possibly those of ritual performers who impersonate the gods and spirits). They contain expressions of negative emotions such as sad longing, though in most of these pieces it is difficult to fully determine whether it expresses the perspective of the divine beings or of the ritual specialists.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature

– Specify: We do not learn much about the features of these supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– Yes

Notes: Each piece in the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) poetic suite is addressed to a god or types of spirits, collectively evoking the possibility of something akin to a pantheon of supernatural beings associated with nature. The sequence of the poems roughly suggests a hierarchy, for it begins with sky gods such as "The Great Unity, The August Lord of the East" (Donghuang taiyi 東皇太一) and "The Lord within the Clouds" (Yunzhong jun 雲中君) and ends with songs to a mountain ghost and to fallen warriors. Other poems in the suites are addressed to the god and goddess of the Xiang River 湘, Masters of Fate, the sun god, and the Earl of the Yellow River.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Organized hierarchically?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Power of beings is domain specific?

– Yes

Notes: Some of the gods appear to be associated with specific rivers, such as the Xiang River or the Yellow River.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other organization of pantheon?

– Specify: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– I don't know

Notes: Traditional scholarship, by and large, interprets the speaker of the first poem of this corpus, "Li sao," as the minister Qu Yuan. More recent scholarship points out that the language of the opening lines suggests the descent of a divine being. The desire to transgress the separation between the human and the divine is thematized by the Chuci genre, through topos such as failed trysts with a goddess or attempts to transcend the heavenly gate.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Notes: The text mentions the high god (di 帝), various deities (majority of whom are associated with nature), human spirits (hun 魂 and po 魄), and monsters dwelling in exotic outskirts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– Yes

Notes: In the framing narrative of "Summoning the Soul" (Zhao hun 招魂), the high god (di 帝) communicates with the "wu" 巫 (spirit-medium).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are other categories of beings present?

– Other [specify]: Monstrous

Notes: The three "Summons" (zhao 招) chapters enumerate exotic creatures at the outer extremes of the world in order to inspire fear in the wandering spirits and hasten their homecoming. Examples of such monsters include soul-catching giants, cannibals, venomous cobra, and nine-headed serpent.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Notes: This is largely absent from the /Chuci zhangju/ except for in the "Heavenly Question" (Tianwen 天問) chapter, where the high god(s) (di 帝) do appear to punish or support several heroes and rulers, but their motivations are not entirely clear. Since the Han period interpreters have found this chapter to be particularly difficult. Wang Yi's commentary often reads such /di/ figures as earthly rulers comparable to the emperors of China's imperial period, who also referred to themselves as /di/.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Notes: This is largely absent from the /Chuci zhangju/ except for in the "Heavenly Question" (Tianwen 天問) chapter, where the high god(s) (di 帝) do appear to punish or support several heroes and rulers, but their motivations are not entirely clear. Since the Han period interpreters have found this chapter to be particularly difficult. Wang Yi's commentary often reads such /di/ figures as earthly rulers comparable to the emperors of China's imperial period, who also referred to themselves as /di/.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Notes: This is largely absent from the /Chuci zhangju/ except for in the "Heavenly Question" (Tianwen 天問) chapter, where the high god(s) (di 帝) do appear to punish or support several heroes and rulers, but their motivations are not entirely clear. Since the Han period interpreters have found this chapter to be particularly difficult. Wang Yi's commentary often reads such /di/ figures as earthly rulers comparable to the emperors of China's imperial period, who also referred to themselves as /di/.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

Notes: One of the central moral dilemmas revolves around how to navigate a corrupt age: whether to conform to its norms in the interest of self-preservation or to uphold what it considers to be universal morality. The "Divination" (Buju 卜居) and "The Fisherman" (Yufu 漁父) chapters, for example, clearly articulate this binary.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– Only one class of society

Notes: This is not entirely clear. In one interpretation, this text expresses largely the moral stance of the male elite shi 士 class.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

– All individuals (any time period)

Notes: Even though during the imperial period, readers largely interpret the protagonists of Chuci as male literati elites, the text does not dictate that its values are restricted to only one specific social group. At least one woman writer, Wu Zao 吴藻 (1799-1862), has written a literary work (a play entitled "Qiao ying 乔影") imitating Qu Yuan.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Courage (in battle)

– Yes

Notes: "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) praises the fallen soldiers for their courage.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Courage (generic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

Notes: Another recurring motif is the protagonists' spotless purity (expressed through terms such as "qing" 清, "jie" 潔, and "bai" 白) despite the constant threat of impurity and corruption. A related motif is the protagonists donning and consuming fragrant plants and flora, which are sources of purity but are not free from the danger of decay.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Fidelity/loyalty

– Yes

Notes: The protagonists in many of the Chuci poems, such as "Li sao" and "Jiu zhang," lament that their integrity, loyalty, and moral rectitude are not recognized by the "Fair One" (meiren 美人), and that they are misunderstood because of others' slanders. They are alone in upholding such virtues in an age of corruption.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Cooperation

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Independence/creativity/freedom

– Yes

Notes: In the sense that the protagonists are independent from their social contexts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Moderation/frugality

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Strength (physical)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Power/status/nobility

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Humility/modesty

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Optimism/hope

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Gratitude/thankfulness

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Reverence/awe/wonder

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Wisdom/understanding

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Discernment/intelligence

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Beauty/attractiveness

– Yes

Notes: The term "beauty" (mei 美) is frequently employed in the early chapters as a positive term, in both physical and metaphorical senses.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness

– Yes

Notes: Another recurring motif is the protagonists' spotless purity (expressed through terms such as "qing" 清, "jie" 潔, and "bai" 白) despite the constant threat of impurity and corruption. A related motif is the protagonists donning and consuming fragrant plants and flora, which are sources of purity but are not free from the danger of decay.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

↳ Other important virtues

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require castration?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Notes: The moral justification for the archpoet Qu Yuan's purported suicide was a source of debate during the Han period. The voices of protagonists occasionally articulate the preference for death over compromising their moral integrity. At the same time, self-sacrifice is not required.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

— Yes

Notes: The "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece of the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) suite celebrates the fallen soldiers. The title and opening lines of "A Lament for Ying" (Ai Ying 哀郢) seem to suggest that it intends to elegize the conquest and destruction of the capital of the Chu state, Ying 郢, but the majority of the poem makes no specific reference to warfare, and is more akin to a poem on exile.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

— An empire

Notes: During the time period specified, the imperial courts of the Western Han, the short-lived Xin dynasty, and Eastern Han operated a centralized bureaucracy that exerted control and extracted resources from a multiplicity of peoples and ethnicities as well as regions that were once all but independent kingdoms. The formation history of /Chuci zhangju/ reflects a process of interaction between the central court and local cultures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Scholar-officials. Over the course of the two Han dynasties, the scholar-officials (shi 士) emerged as a new form of elite identity. They were largely responsible for the production and reproduction of elite literary writings during China's imperial period. While the early formation history of the Chuci materials could have involved ritual performers, religious specialists, as well as the clients patronized by the king of Huainan, its later authors, compilers, and commentators—including Wang Yi—were scholar-officials, namely bureaucrats who held official positions in the Han government and whose elite social position was partly defined by their literary and scholarly skills and activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– An empire

Notes: During the time period specified, the imperial courts of the Western Han, the short-lived Xin dynasty, and Eastern Han operated a centralized bureaucracy that exerted control and extracted resources from a multiplicity of peoples and ethnicities as well as regions that were once all but independent kingdoms. The formation history of /Chuci zhangju/ reflects a process of interaction between the central court and local cultures.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Scholar-officials. Over the course of the two Han dynasties, the scholar-officials (shi 士) emerged as a new form of elite identity. They were largely responsible for the production and reproduction of elite literary writings during China's imperial period. While the early formation history of the Chuci materials could have involved ritual performers, religious specialists, as well as the clients patronized by the king of Huainan, its later authors, compilers, and commentators—including Wang Yi—were scholar-officials, namely bureaucrats who held official positions in the Han government and whose elite social position was partly defined by their literary and scholarly skills and activities.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– Other

Notes: None

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

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Specific to this answer:

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– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text dictate how to control an institutionalized military?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text restrict/advocate for participation in exogenous military organizations?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Does the text celebrate/bemoan protection/subjugation by an exogenous military force?

– Yes

Notes: The "Hymn to the Fallen" (Guo shang 國殤) piece of the "Nine Songs" (Jiu ge 九歌) suite celebrates the fallen soldiers. The title and opening lines of "A Lament for Ying" (Ai Ying 哀郢) seem to suggest that it intends to elegize the conquest and destruction of the capital of the Chu state, Ying 郢, but the majority of the poem makes no specific reference to warfare, and is more akin to a poem on exile.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Han

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